

Separation of Nickel by Solvent Extraction and Cation-Exchange. Determination of Nickel in Mineral Waters

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A method for the isolation of nickel from mineral waters by solvent extraction and cation exchange is described. The nickel is first preconcentrated from the waters by chloroform extraction in its dimethylglyoximate form at pH 7.4-7.6. The chloroform extract is then mixed with THF and methanol containing hydrochloric acid, and passed through a column of Dowex 50-X8 (H⁺ form). After removal of dimethylglyoxime, chloroform and THF by washing the resin with methanol-HCl, nickel is eluted with 6M HCl and determined by a.a.s. with an air-acetylene flame. The method was successfully applied to determine nickel in bottled mineral waters in which nickel in the range from 0.3 to 30 µg Ni/litre was found.

THE determination of trace quantities of nickel in natural waters and waste waters is gaining increasing importance with the growing interest in pollution of the environment with this and other heavy metals.

Preconcentration of nickel, mainly together with several other metal pollutants, is carried out before its quantitative determination. For isolation of trace amounts of nickel from natural and waste waters the best separation methods are based on liquid-liquid extraction of nickel with dithiocarbamates or as other nickel complexes¹⁻¹⁰.

In the present paper, a combination of separation techniques is described, which utilizes chloroform extraction of nickel dimethylglyoximate as the first preconcentration step followed by cation-exchange enrichment of nickel directly from the organic extract.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents :

The strongly acidic cation exchanger Dowex 50-X8 (Bio-Rad AG 50W-X8, 100-200 mesh ; H⁺ form) was used. A slurry of the resin (4 g) was prepared with a few ml of 6 M HCl and poured into the ion-exchanger column using 50 ml of the same acid as a rinse and to purify the exchanger. Subsequently, the resin was washed with tetrahydrofuran (THF) prior to pretreatment of samples.

Standard solutions of Ni(II) in 6 M HCl was prepared from a stock solution containing 1 mg Ni(II) per ml of 6M HCl. MeOH-HCl mixture with 1 M overall acidity was prepared by diluting 85 ml conc. HCl to 1 litre with methanol. 10 ml of this diluted to 100 ml with methanol gave the MeOH-HCl mixture of 0.1M overall acidity, which is used for the ion-exchange separation of nickel. CHCl₃-THF-MeOH solution of 0.1 M overall

acidity was prepared by mixing 30 ml of CHCl₃ with 60 ml of THF and 10 ml of MeOH-HCl mixture of 1 M overall acidity. Other reagents used were 10% aqueous solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, aqueous ammonia (1 : 1) and a 10% solution of dimethylglyoxime in ethanol.

For the determination of nickel, a Perkin-Elmer Atomic Absorption Spectrometer Model 303 was used with the following instrumental settings : uv grating ; wavelength 232.5 nm ; scale expansion up to 2X ; slit width 3 (0.3-0.2 nm bandpass) ; nickel hollow-cathode lamp at 25-40 mA ; standard burner head ; acetylene pressure 8 psig (7.0 on flow meter scale) ; air pressure 30 psig (9.0 on flow meter scale) ; noise suppression up to 2.

When the measurements were done with 6 M hydrochloric acid solutions, a sensitivity (1% absorption) of 0.24 ppm of nickel was obtained.

The ion-exchange columns used for the separation of nickel from the organic extracts were of the type and dimensions described earlier¹¹.

Determination of distribution coefficients : The distribution coefficients (K_d-values) of nickel in the various media employed for the cation exchange separations were determined by using the batch method¹².

Procedure :

To 0.5-1.0 litre of the water sample are added 10 ml of conc. HCl and 5 ml of the hydroxylamine hydrochloride solution. The pH of the mixture is adjusted to 7.4 to 7.6 by the addition of dilute ammonia solution (1 : 1) and it is transferred to a 2 litre separatory funnel using a few ml of water as a rinse. 5 ml of the dimethylglyoxime solution is added to the sample mixture and shaken for 1 min. The nickel dimethylglyoximate is extracted with 20 ml of chloroform using a shaking time of 5 min.

The extraction is repeated with two 20 ml portions of chloroform, shaking 2 min each time. The three extracts are combined.

To the combined chloroform extracts (about 60 ml) is added 20 ml of the MeOH-HCl mixture (overall acidity 1 M) and diluted with 120 ml of THF. The resulting solution (the sorption solution, overall acidity 0.1 M) is passed through a 4 g column of the cation exchanger (pretreated with 20 ml of the CHCl_3 -THF-MeOH solution) at a flow rate of about 1.7 ml/min. The resin bed is washed with 5 ml CHCl_3 -THF-MeOH solution, 10 ml of MeOH-HCl mixture (overall acidity 0.1 M) and 5 ml 0.1 M hydrochloric acid in this order. The nickel is then eluted with 100 ml of 6 M HCl.

The eluate is evaporated to dryness on a steam-bath and the residue is dissolved in 10 ml of 6 M hydrochloric acid. This solution is aspirated into the air-acetylene flame. Calibration curves are constructed by aspirating suitable standard solutions of nickel before and after each batch of samples.

Results and Discussion

Separation of nickel :

Atomic-absorption measurements of the nickel in the chloroform extracts did not give either the required sensitivity or reproducible results. The nickel was therefore stripped from the organic phase using dilute HCl and the assay was completed after wet-ashing of the co-extracted organic compounds. However, this very tedious procedure was abandoned in favour of the ion-exchange technique described in the procedure which in combination with the extraction step gave results of high accuracy and reproducibility. It is seen from Table 1 that this procedure allows the quantitative isolation of both μg and mg amounts of nickel.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION ON NICKEL RECOVERY FROM TAP WATER

Amount of nickel added to 1 litre of water sample, μg	Nickel found $\mu\text{g/litre}$	%
12	11.8	98.5
100	103	103
500	512	102.5
1000	998	99.8

By means of the ion-exchange procedure the nickel is separated from the chelating agent dimethylglyoxime and chloroform without the need of evaporation or back-extraction and wet-ashing. The presence of tetrahydrofuran is necessary in the CHCl_3 -THF-MeOH solution to obtain a homogeneous solution, and methanol is the component regulating the flow rate through the ion-exchange column. In absence of methanol, the viscosity of the sorption solution is extremely low and a very

high flow rate is attained at which complete adsorption of nickel is not assured. Hydrochloric acid has to be present in the mixture so that the nickel remains in the ionic form which is adsorbed on the cation-exchanger during the sorption process. After adsorption, the residual chloroform, tetrahydrofuran and dimethylglyoxime are removed by washing the resin bed with the MeOH-HCl mixture.

The measurement of the batch distribution coefficients of nickel in all the media employed for the cation-exchange separation of this element gave the results for K_d as 1940 in CHCl_3 -THF-MeOH medium, 4380 in MeOH-HCl mixture, and 977 and <1 in 0.1 and 6 M HCl, respectively.

Nickel is thus found to be very strongly retained by the resin from the organic as well as aqueous 0.1 M hydrochloric acid solutions so that this method is suitable for the quantitative separation of both μg and mg amounts of this element.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATIONS OF NICKEL IN SAMPLES OF BOTTLED MINERAL WATER

Trade name	Nickel content $\mu\text{g/litre}$	
	A	B
Bonaqua	0.25	0.26
Petersquelle	0.34	0.34
Ausseer Heilquelle	0.53	0.54
Römerquelle	1.30	1.33
Sixtina	2.89	2.99
Donat	3.49	3.51
Severinquelle	3.87	3.63
Güssinger	4.84	4.82
Vitusbrunnen	5.24	5.15
Radenska	5.22	5.38
Preßblauer (Ebriachquelle)	29.9	29.8

A—Nickel contents determined by a.s.s. following solvent extraction and cation-exchange of nickel.

B—Same as for A, but after deduction of 2.0 μg Ni added to the sample before application of the procedure.

Application to natural waters :

Table 2 gives the results obtained when this procedure was applied to the analysis of 11 mineral water samples.

Comparison of the results listed in columns A and B of Table 2 shows that the amounts of nickel added were recovered quantitatively in all cases, i.e. nickel is not lost during the separation procedures.

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